

Influence of pH on hanging mercury drop electrode cyclic voltammetry with aspartic acid in acetate buffers

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Abstract : As the supporting electrolyte (acetate buffer) itself interacts with mercury, the Hg-acetate current is always superimposed on the Hg-amino acid interaction current. Hence whether amino acid is present or not there will be the current of Hg-acetate leading to intercept on the current axis of the I_p vs [aspartic acid] plot. There are three processes deduced from Hg-amino acid solution interaction. They are process A, B and C. Process A is due to mercuric mercury complex formation, $Hg^0 + (asp) \leftrightarrow Hg^{2+} (asp)$ and process B is due to mercurous mercury complex formation, $Hg^0 + (asp) \leftrightarrow Hg_2^{2+} (asp)$. Process C is the result of mercury-acetate interaction. The peak potentials are shifted to less positive values with increasing pH.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, mercury, aspartic acid, acetate buffer, HMDE.

Introduction

Mercury pollution continues to remain as a major threat to life. Mercury is released into the environment as waste by products from metallurgical process and industries such as chloroalkali, paint, agriculture, pharmaceutical and paper and pulp industries with which mercury is associated in different capacities (such as electrodes, catalysts etc.). These enter the food chain of living systems. The solubility of inorganic and organic mercury compounds in lipids as well as their binding to proteins in membranes and enzymes account for their toxicity. Amino acids being the basic constituents of proteins, the interactions of mercury with proteins are best studied by analyzing its reaction with the individual amino acids.

Earlier, the interaction of mercury with amino acids such as tryptophan and histidine using various polarographic techniques were studied¹⁻⁶. Aspartic acid and glutamic acid are dicarboxylic amino acids and important members of amino acid family with a single carbon variation. However the mercury dissolution experiment was not applied to these amino acids. Further, all the reported analysis was carried out using old analytical techniques such as ac and dc polarography. Novel technique such as cyclic voltammetry was not applied in these cases. Recently the oxidation state and coordination were analysed for vanadium containing molecular sieves by cyclic voltammetry⁷⁻¹⁰. It is interesting to know the electrochemical reaction of mercury with amino acids. The mercury interaction with glutamic acid was reported re-

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of mercury dissolution in the presence of 2 mM of aspartic acid in different acetate buffers of pHs (1) 4.4, (2) 5.5 and (3) 6.4, scan rate = 50 mV/s.

Table 1. Comparison of anodic and cathodic potentials of cyclic voltammograms of mercury dissolution in aspartic acid in varying concentrations in different pHs 4.4, 5.5 and 6.4
Scan rate = 50 mV/s

[asp] (mM)	pH							
	4.4		5.5			6.4		
	E_{pa} (V) vs SCE	E_{pc} (V) vs SCE	E_{pa} (V) vs SCE	E_{pc} (V) vs SCE		E_{pa} (V) vs SCE	E_{pc} (V) vs SCE	
			c_1	c_2		c_1	c_2	
0	0.535	0.210	-	-	0.175	0.535	-	0.170
0.06	0.545	0.25	-	-	0.175	0.56	-	-
0.1	0.495	0.20	-	-	0.175	0.56	-	-
0.125	0.525	0.185	-	-	0.175	0.522	0.275	0.22
0.25	0.525	0.185	-	-	0.175	0.495	0.275	0.22
0.5	0.525	0.185	-	-	-	0.46	0.28	0.23
0.75	0.535	0.18	-	-	-	0.455	0.28	0.23
1.0	0.54	0.18	0.52	-	0.23	0.44	0.285	0.24
1.5	0.545	0.175	0.515	-	0.24	0.435	0.285	0.24
2	0.54	0.175	0.47	-	0.285	0.43	0.28	0.24
4	0.54	0.185	0.45	-	0.28	0.42	-	0.25
6	-	-	0.44	0.32	0.275	0.415	0.275	0.25
8	0.545	0.205	0.435	0.32	0.275	0.415	-	0.255
10	0.545	0.2	-	-	-	0.41	-	0.26
12	0.545	0.19	0.425	0.325	0.275	0.41	-	0.26
14	0.54	0.19	0.425	0.335	0.275	0.41	-	0.26
16	-	-	0.42	0.345	0.275	0.41	-	0.26
18	-	0.225	0.42	0.345	0.27	0.41	-	0.265
20	-	0.23	-	0.27	0.345	0.41	-	0.27
25	-	0.25	0.41	0.395	0.27	0.38	-	0.265

cently¹¹, however aspartic acid was not attended despite its importance in human biological system. In this study, the electroanalytical (cyclic voltammetric) interaction of mercury with aspartic acid in acetate buffers were carried out. pH values such as 4.4, 5.5 and 6.4 were chosen for the study.

Experimental

L(-) Aspartic acid (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, India), potassium nitrate (G.R., Loba-Chemie Indoaustranal Co., India), sodium acetate trihydrate (A.R., Fisher Inorganics and Aromatics Ltd., India), glacial acetic acid (A.R., s.d.finc, India), mercury (G.R., E. Merck, India) were used without further purification.

Hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) was prepared in the following procedure : A platinum electrode of area approximately one square mm was sealed to a soft glass tube in such a way that the platinum to glass seal was smooth and convex in shape. This ensured all exposed platinum to be covered with mercury drop. A pool of mercury at the bottom of the electrochemical cell served as the

counter electrode. Saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. All the experiments were carried out in an air-conditioned room at 25 ± 2 °C.

Cyclic voltammetry unit was assembled using a voltage scan generator (Wenking model VSG 83, Bonk Electronics, West Germany) and standard Potentiostat (Wenking ST72, Bonk Electronics, West Germany). Voltammograms were recorded using an x-y recorder (Type WX 2300, Graphic Corporation, Japan).

Results and discussion

Well defined anodic and cathodic waves are formed in the cyclic voltammogram of mercury dissolution in acetate buffer of pH 4.4. The difference between the cathodic and anodic peak potentials viz. $E_{pc} - E_{pa} = 225$ mV. The ratio of cathodic peak current to anodic peak current, $I_{pc}/I_{pa} = 0.48$ in the buffer of pH 4.4. However no such analysis could be done for the cyclic voltammograms of mercury acetate interactions in buffers of pH 5.5 and 6.4. This is due to the ill-defined nature of anodic waves. The cathodic waves have normal

Fig. 2. Change in anodic (—x—, I_{pa}) and cathodic (—o—, I_{pc}) peak currents with respect to [asp] concentration in acetate buffer of pH 4.4.

shape. The cathodic peak potential E_{pc} shifts to less positive values with increasing pH.

pH 4.4 :

Single anodic and cathodic waves are observed in the cyclic voltammograms of mercury dissolution in the pres-

ence of aspartic acid in pH 4.4. In general, the anodic peak potential E_{pa} shifts to more positive values with increasing concentration of aspartic acid. E_{pa} remains constant around 540 ± 5 mV in the concentration range of 0.75 to 14 mM of aspartic acid. The cathodic peak

Fig. 3. Change in anodic (—x—, I_{pa}) and cathodic (—o—, I_{pc}) peak currents with respect to [asp] concentration in acetate buffer of pH 5.5.

Fig. 4. Change in anodic ($-x-$, I_{pa}) and cathodic ($-o-$, I_{pc}) peak currents with respect to [asp] concentration in acetate buffer of pH 6.4.

potential, E_{pc} also remains constant in the concentration range 4 to 0.125 mM at 180 ± 5 mV. In the lower concentration range of 4 to 0.06 mM, E_{pc} shifts to more positive values with decreasing [asp], while in the concentration range of 10 to 25 mM, E_{pc} shifts to more positive values with increase in [asp] (Table 1).

The variation in peak currents both anodic (I_{pa}) and cathodic (I_{pc}) follow the same trend with change in [asp] (Fig. 2). There is an exponential increase in peak currents from a concentration of 2 mM reaching a maximum value at 8 mM of aspartic acid. Thereafter it decreases with increasing aspartic acid concentration. Anodic waves of cyclic voltammograms corresponding to the concentration range of 6 to 25 mM of aspartic acid registered at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} are all rounded for which precise measurement of E_{pa} becomes difficult (Table 1) and $I_{pa} > I_{pc}$ for all concentrations.

pH 5.5 :

Well defined anodic and cathodic waves are seen in the presence of aspartic acid of concentration in the range of 2 to 25 mM. The single cathodic wave separates into two waves C_1 and C_2 in the presence of 4 to 25 mM of aspartic acid. The anodic waves for concentrations below 4 mM have distorted shapes.

The anodic and cathodic peak currents (Fig. 3) vary with change in [asp] in an exponential manner. Anodic peak current (I_{pa}) varies linearly with square root of scan rate indicating the anodic process to be diffusion controlled (Fig. 5).

Anodic peak potential (E_{pa}) shifts to less positive potentials with increasing [asp]. It is 520 mV at 1.0 mM which changes to 410 mV at 25 mM of aspartic acid.

Cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}) shifts to more positive values with increasing concentration of aspartic acid. e.g. E_{pc1} value of 300 mV at 4 mM changes to 395 mV at 25 mM, while peak potential E_{pc2} remains constant at 275 ± 5 mV in the concentration range of 2 to 25 mM and decreases to 175 mV with decreasing concentration of aspartic acid from 2 to 0.06 mM (Table 1).

Anodic potentials shift to more positive values while cathodic potentials become less positive with increasing scan rates. The split in the cathodic wave occurs at scan rates of 50 mV s^{-1} and above.

pH 6.4 :

The cathodic wave of the cyclic voltammogram at low concentrations of aspartic acid viz. 0.06 and 0.1 mM are broad splitting into two waves c_1 and c_2 at a much earlier concentration of 0.125 mM. This split persists only up to 6 mM of aspartic acid. This is in contrast to C_1 and C_2 of buffer of pH 5.5, which appear at much later concentration of 4 mM persisting down to the highest concentration of 25 mM (Fig. 1).

Peak currents I_{pa} and I_{pc} decrease exponentially from 1.5 mM to 25 mM (Fig. 4). Anodic peak currents vary linearly with square root of scan rate indicating the process to be diffusion controlled (Fig. 5).

Anodic peak potential, E_{pa} becomes less positive with increasing concentrations of aspartic acid, while the ca-

Fig. 5. The variation in anodic peak current with square root of scan rate for the cyclic voltammograms of anodic dissolution of mercury in the presence of aspartic acid in acetate buffers at different [asp] concentration.

thodic peak potential E_{pc1} remains constant around 280 ± 5 mV. The peak potential E_{pc2} corresponding to the cathodic wave c_2 shifts to more positive values with increasing [asp]. This leads to merging of waves c_1 and c_2 at higher concentrations of aspartic acid (Table 1).

Peak potential, E_{pa} becomes more anodic and E_{pc2} more cathodic with increasing scan rate.

Conclusions :

The supporting electrolyte (acetate buffer) itself interacts with mercury. So the Hg-acetate current is always superimposed on the Hg-amino acid interaction current. Hence whether amino acid is present or not there will be the current of Hg-acetate interaction leading to the intercept on the current axis of the I_p vs [aspartic acid] plot. The exponential decrease in I_{pc} and I_{pa} at high concentrations of amino acids is due to blocking of the electrode surface by the products of mercury-amino acid interactions. Hence the blocking of the electrode surface is determined not only

by potential but also by [aspartic acid]. There are three processes (A, B and C) observed on Hg-amino acid solution interaction. Process A is due to mercuric mercury complex formation, $Hg^0 + (asp) \leftrightarrow Hg^{2+} (asp)$ and process B is due to mercurous mercury complex formation, $Hg^0 + (asp) \leftrightarrow Hg_2^{2+} (asp)$. Process C is due to mercury-acetate interaction. With increasing pH, the potentials are shifted to less positive values.

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